

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF THE VIBRATION PROPERTIES OF 3D BRAIDED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper is to investigate the vibration characteristics of three-dimensional(3D) braided composites with different braiding parameters consisting of braiding structure, braiding angle and fiber volume fraction. The natural frequencies of the first three order were excited with hammer and the test data were scattered and fitted in normalized frequency(F), fiber content(V_f) and normalized braiding angle(A_f) space. The results show that the natural frequency of braided composite increases when the braiding angle reduces or the fiber content rises. In the 3D four-directional(4d) structure the natural frequency is strongly dependent on the braiding angle showing a nearly parabolic relationship, the fiber content acts the increasingly determinant factor as the braiding angle declines. As a transitional structure, the 3D5d braided structure presents some uncertainty, the fiber volume fraction plays a decisive role upon the nature frequency along the directional derivative $dV_f/dA_f=0$. With saturation of the axial yarns, the f5d braiding structure shows more stability compared with others since it presents a strong linear relationship with the braiding angle. Therefore, the vibration frequency of this material is strongly designable and the braiding angle and the fiber volume fraction should be considered as two major factors. These findings have great significance for further dynamic research of braided composites.

1 Introduction

The 3D braided composite, a textile technology developed in 1980s, has created a new class of composite materials and fundamentally overcome the disadvantages of traditional laminated structure. The principal feature of 3D braided materials that makes them desirable for reinforcing composites is the ability to form different geometric shapes and other advantages of this class of composites include better energy absorbing capability, higher delamination resistance and impact damage tolerance compared to 2D laminates. As a result, this material has attracted lots of attention and has been widely used in aerospace, military, biomedical and sporting goods [1-3].

Although a lot of research work has been done extensively focusing on elastic properties of braided materials and made considerable achievements in recent years[4-20], little attention was paid to the

mechanical properties of 3Df5d braided composites, a more stable braiding structure [21,22], especially the vibration characteristics of them.

Based on the approach of modified classical laminated plate and the theory of energy dissipation, Cai [23] investigated the stiffness and the damping of the rectangular cross-section links with 3D4d braided composite. Particularly, he derived the formulations for calculating the stiffness coefficients and specific damping capacity. Using double Fourier series, Huang[24] presented the analytical solution of free vibration for simply supported 3D4d shear deformable plate based on Reddy's theory of higher order shear deformable plate. In this study, the effects of fiber volume fractions and braiding angle on natural frequencies were also investigated. Li[25] conducted a thorough study on 3D4d and 3D5d braided composites using the method of free vibration of cantilever beams. It has been demonstrated that the damping properties of composites are improved while the braiding angle increases or the fiber volume fraction decreases. Additionally, the damping properties of the 3D5d structure are superior to those of 3D4d braiding structure. Based on the mesostructure and unit cell model, Lu[26] investigated the vibration properties of 3D4d and 3D5d rectangular cross-section braided composite cantilever beams. The law of vibration characteristics influenced by braiding parameters was developed by theoretical analysis. This study especially emphasized nonlinear properties of the loss factor related to braiding parameters. Gao[27] systematically studied the free vibration characteristics of 3D5d braided composites with different braiding angles with a simple testing system. The first three order modes of composite specimens with different braiding angles were obtained and discussed. The result reveals that braiding angle is a crucial factor for vibration design of 3D5d braided composites. Pei[28,29] explored the effect rule of the microstructure and braiding parameters on the dynamic behavior of 3D4d braided composites using a discrete beam model. In addition, he also investigated the effect of damage on the modal properties of a 3D4d T-beam by means of experiment and simulation. Wan[30] also proposed that the method of real-time health monitoring of 3D4d braided composites using carbon nanotube threads is feasible.

In order to explore the vibration property of 3D braided composites, a systematic experiment firstly considering the braiding structure was implemented in this paper. Through free vibration response in the cantilever system, the first three order natural frequencies were excited and compared. And then the braiding parameters, namely braiding structure, braiding angle and fiber volume fraction, were discussed in detail about its effect on the natural frequency respectively, providing a reference for further dynamic research of braided composites.

2 Braiding parameters

1×1 4-step(or row and column) braiding process, which can be automatically controlled, is the most common way to produce braided composites. Every 4 steps is completed by one machine cycle. In the first machine step, alternate rows of yarn carriers are moved in opposite x-directions; in the second machine step, alternate columns are moved in opposite y-directions; the third and fourth machine steps are similar to the first two steps, but in the reverse directions[2]. As one braiding cycle is accomplished, a periodic topological structure can be formed, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Periodic topological structure

The variables l , w , h refer to braiding pitch length, braiding pitch width and braiding pitch height, respectively. It should be noted that majority of previous work have assumed that l is identical to w , this is not appropriate in reality. The parameter characterized by α with respect to the z axis refers to the braiding angle, which cannot be measured directly but can be determined by l , w , and h from surface measurement. The relationship between these parameters can be given as:

$$\tan \alpha = \frac{\sqrt{l^2 + w^2}}{h} \quad (1)$$

The number of yarns used for producing preforms is identified as the total number of carriers, and it is calculated using the formulas as follows:

$$N_4 = mn + m + n \quad (2)$$

$$N_5 = 2mn + m + n \quad (3)$$

$$N_{f5} = 3mn + 1 \quad (4)$$

in which m is the number of carriers in each row, n is the number of carriers in each column, and the subscript of N refers to braiding structures.

In addition, fiber volume fraction denoted as V_f is given as:

$$V_f = \frac{m_p}{\rho V_s} \quad (5)$$

where m_p is the mass of preforms, ρ is the density of carbon yarns, and V_s represents the volume of the test sample.

3 Experiment

3.1 Specimens

All preforms, 12 groups for each type of structure, were produced by Beijing 3D Braiding Co., Ltd with different braiding angles and fiber volume fractions. These preforms were consolidated with epoxy resin into the final samples using the Resin Transfer Molding(RTM) method. Three structures consisting of 4d, 5d and f5d are involved in the preforms.

The carbon fiber and matrix are T700-12K and EpoTech4237 epoxy resin, respectively. The mechanical properties of them are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of carbon and epoxy resin

Material	E_{11} /Gpa	E_{22} /Gpa	G_{13} /Gpa	G_{23} /Gpa	μ_{12}
T700-12K	230	40	24	14.3	0.26
EpoTech4237	4.5	-	-	-	0.3

The size of specimen is ensured to be 250mm (length) \times 25mm (width) \times 5mm (thickness) by a specific mold with 2 parallelized flow passages, as illustrated in Figure 2. Particularly, in order to provide a better cantilever boundary condition and also to avoid any damage to the specimen during the test, the end of the beam was symmetrically strengthened with two aluminum plates (50mm \times 25mm \times 5mm) using high-strength epoxy glue. Thus, the effective dimension of the cantilever was reduced to 200mm (length) \times 25mm (width) \times 5mm (thickness).

Figure 2. Mold specification

3.2 Method and equipment

In this study, the experiment aims to obtain the first three frequencies of specimens with different braiding parameters. Considering the thermodynamics properties of materials, the environment temperature was set to 25°C to ensure more stable results. With the method of free damped vibration, the signal was collected in a cantilever system through hammer excitation approach due to its simplicity and efficiency. For accuracy, the final frequency-domain signal for each sample was calculated by averaging 10 excited signals.

Figure 3. Experimental test setups

During the experiment, the accelerometer Kistler(8202A10) with sensitivity of 10pC/g was adhesively mounted near the free-end of the sample, as shown in Figure 3, whereas near the fixed-end of it the vibration signal was excited. The frequency width was controlled to cover 0-3000Hz by the

hammer head. In addition, other laboratory equipment, such as the clamp, signal amplifier and Digital Signal Processing(DSP) instrument, were also included.

4 Results analysis

4.1 Relationships of natural frequencies

To analyze the relationship of natural frequencies, the ratios of the second to the first order natural frequency (r_1) and the third to the second order natural frequency (r_2) are calculated respectively for each test group, as shown in Figure 4. It can be clearly seen that there is an obvious proportional relationship among the first three natural frequencies. Despite the braiding parameters, the ratio r_1 of all specimens fluctuates at about 7.0, while r_2 keeps the level of 3.0. Particularly, the data in Refs.[27,28] can offer some evidence to these findings. These results indicate that the theory of linear vibration in continuum mechanics is available to some extent for 3D braided materials. As a conclusion, to investigate effects of braiding parameters on the natural frequencies of this kind material, we can safely take the first order natural frequency as an reference.

Figure 4. Ratios of the nature frequency in (a) 3D4d, (b) 3D5d and (c) 3Df5d structures.

4.2 Influences of braiding structures on the natural frequency

For the sake of generalization, the normalization method is adopted to analyze the test data. The normalized frequency F , which can directly reflect the data gradient, is defined as the ratio of the first order natural frequency to the maximum value in the same braiding structure. Likewise, the normalized braiding angle denoted by A_f is defined as $\alpha/90^\circ$, however, considering its dimensionless character, V_f is reserved. The experimental data were scattered and fitted as 3D surfaces in the F - A_f - V_f space with Origin.

Figure 5. Fitting surface

5d and (c) 3Df5d structures.

As shown in Figure 5, It is obvious of the non-linear relationship for the 4d structure in $F-A_f-V_f$ space. Regarding 5d and f5d structures, the test data scatter almost near a plane showing a linear trend, especially the f5d structure. From the mesostructural perspective, this is because of the fact that the axial yarn can contribute structural stability along the braiding direction and thus linearize the axial mechanical variation. Therefore the more proportion of axial yarns is, the stronger the linearity shows. The 3D5d structure is more like a transitional braiding pattern from the 3D4d to 3Df5d structure.

4.3 Influences of braiding angles on the natural frequency

The braiding angle plays an important role in the vibration behavior of braided materials. As shown in Figure 6, generally, with the same fiber content, the nature frequency rises as braiding angle decreases and drops when braiding angle increases in three structure patterns.

In order to explore how the braiding angle affects the frequency, profiles of each structure are presented at $V_f=0.45$ and $A_f=0.35$. Specifically, from Figure 6a, the relationships between the braiding angle and natural frequency in 3D4d structures show almost parabolic characteristics. Larger braiding angle corresponds to higher frequency change rate and smaller braiding angle corresponds to lower frequency change rate. In 3Df5d structures, the sensitivity of the natural frequency to the braiding angle keeps constant apparently. This reflects that for this structure the braiding angle almost has no influence on the changing rate of the natural frequency. However, in 3D5d structures, this trend are not monotonous as shown in Figure 6b when A_f and V_f are more than 0.4, respectively.

This is due to the fact that the orientation of braiding yarns determines the axial modulus which play

the dominant role in the vibration behavior of cantilever beams. Small braiding angle leads to high axial stiffness and large braiding angle results in low axial stiffness accordingly. As mentioned above, with the axial yarns introduced, this trend becomes much more stable.

4.4 Influences of fiber content on the natural frequency

As can be observed in Figure 6, despite the braiding structure, the effect of fiber volume fraction on the natural frequency shows positive correlation with the nature frequency. With the same braiding angle, the nature frequency rises as the fiber content increases, and vice versa.

Figure 6. Profiles of fitting surfaces with $V_f=0.45$ and $A_f=0.35$ in (a) 3D4d, (b) 3D5d and (c) 3Df5d structures.

Based on the data of the 3D4d structure, considering the angle between the gradient orientation and the V_f axis, this angle is obviously smaller than that of other field when the braiding angle decreases, which indicates that in this structure the fiber volume fraction plays increasingly decisive role in affecting the natural frequency as the braiding angle drops down. Accordingly, in 3D5d braided structure, there is almost linear relationship between the fiber volume fraction and nature frequency. As the braiding angle and fiber volume fraction increase, the nature frequency presents a flat region which results from the opposite effect on the natural frequency of the braiding angle and the fiber volume fraction. It is noticeable that the most sensitive direction of fiber content to natural frequency is consistent with $dV_f/dA_f=0$. Regarding the 3Df5d structure, no matter what the braiding angle is, the sensitivity to fiber content declines as the fiber content drops. Moreover, when $A_f=0.35$ and V_f increases from 37.5% to 55.0%, the normalized natural frequency rises from 0.732 to 0.825, the difference quotient equals about 0.53. and the 3D5d and 3Df5d corresponds to the values 1.89 and 0.82, respectively.

These findings indicate that the natural frequency of 3D5d structures is more easily affected by fiber contents with respect to the 3D4d and 3Df5d. This phenomenon might be induced by the instability of the spatial orientation of axial yarns. As mentioned above, in this transitional structure, the fact that the straightness of axial yarn cannot be ensured under the unsymmetrical squeezing circumstance definitely leads to the uncertainty of axial modulus unless the fiber contents are increased.

5 Conclusion

In order to clarify the relationship between braiding parameters and the vibration behavior, the first three natural frequencies were extracted and the structure pattern, braiding angle and fiber content were considered from large amount of samples in our research. This study reveals that:

1. There is a proportional relationship among the first three natural frequencies, which can support the idea that braided materials have the dynamic common with the isotropic homogeneous materials.

2. Generally, the natural frequency of 3D braided composite increases when the braiding angle reduces or the fiber content rises, and vice versa. Specifically, in the 3D4d structure it presents a nearly parabolic relationship with the natural frequency. in the 3D5d structure, this tendency is not monotonous due to that the fiber content plays a decisive role along the directional derivative $dV_f/dA_f=0$. Besides, comparative analysis reveals that the 3Df5d structure possesses the most stability since it presents a strong linear relationship with the braiding angle. On contrary, the effect of fiber content on the natural frequency has an inverse trend compared with the braiding angle, showing positive correlation with the nature frequency. In the 3D4d structure, the fiber content acts the increasingly determinant factor as the braiding angle declines. However, in 3Df5d braided structure, the sensitivity to fiber content decreases as the fiber content drops not affected by the braiding angle almost.

3. The vibration behavior of 3D braided composites is strongly designable. Especially, braiding angles and fiber contents should be the primary terms to take into account. The f5d braiding structure shows more structural stability and thus has quasi-linear mechanical properties compared with others, more attention paid to the 3Df5d structure is recommended.

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